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“Go and Do Likewise:” The Biblical Underpinnings of *Fratelli Tutti*

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Abstract: Pope Francis elaborates seven dark clouds, viz., national interest, polarization, moral deterioration, calamities, absence of human dignity, digital media, and self-contempt, over a closed world. Despite such desperate scenario, he discusses new paths of hope in his Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*. In his attempt to search for a ray of light, he has recourse to the parable ‘The Good Samaritan’ (Luke 10:25-37). Using the selected texts of the Bible, he explicates the concept of neighbour, persuades not to have indifference, commands to love neighbour by obeying the golden rule,

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presents the rationale for fraternity, and declares that love builds bridges. The definition of neighbour based on this parable could be: See not who your neighbour is; see whose neighbour you are. From human perspective whatever we may be, based on our caste, creed, culture, colour, country, Jesus wants us to be the Good Samaritan taking care of the last, the least, and the lost.

Keywords: *Fratelli Tutti*, Indifference, Love, Parable of the Good Samaritan

In the context of the centenary celebration of the arrival of Spanish Jesuits in Gujarat, I came across a snippet about the Spanish Women Congregation called Missionary Society of the Sacred Heart of Jesus. According to that vignette, way back in 1950 the Leprosarium in Surat (Gujarat) belonged to a Parsee Trust. The Trust was convinced that only Catholic Nuns would be willing to work for the lepers. So, the Trust approached the Parish Priest of Surat, a Spanish Jesuit, with a request to arrange for Catholic Nuns from Spain to serve in the Leprosy Hospital. Consequently, on 30th August 1950, the Sisters in Spain received a telegram from Surat with the message: “Be ready, the work at the Leprosy Hospital is being given to you.” Responding to this call, four young Spanish Nuns commenced nursing the lepers in Surat Hospital since 11th February 1951. Not knowing the language, culture, customs, and creed of these patients did not matter a bit to these foreign Sisters, because they believed that they have to be the neighbors of the needy and that *Fratelli Tutti*. Seven decades have passed by since then and still the dedicated service of the Sisters continues till date unabatedly.

“I offer this social Encyclical as a modest contribution to continued reflection, in the hope that in the face of present-day attempts to eliminate or ignore others, we may prove capable of responding with a new vision of fraternity and social friendship that will not remain at the level of words” (FT 5-6) With these sentiments, Pope Francis pens his thoughts apropos of fraternity and social friendship in his Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* given in Assisi on 3rd October 2020, in the eighth year of his Pontificate.

He evaluates the ongoing scenario as the hindrance to the development of universal fraternity. In the First Part of my project, I resonate with his judgment and endorse his theme ‘dark clouds over a closed world,’ wherein he lists seven obstacles to social friendship. The list of seven obstacles includes national interest, polarization, moral deterioration, calamities, absence of human dignity, digital media, and self-contempt. Then, in the Second Part of my project, I examine the biblical underpinnings of his new vision of fraternity and social friendship.

1. The Dark Clouds: Some Factors Obstructing Fraternity

a. National Interest

The first trend that obstructs fraternity constitutes the national interest at the cost of social good. The national interest is highlighted and global economy is advocated. The global economy imposes a single-culture model. “This culture unifies the world, but divides persons and nations, for “as society becomes ever more globalized, it makes us neighbours, but does not make us brothers” (FT 12). The youth are persuaded to ignore their history, to reject the experiences of their elders, to look down on the past, and to look forward to a future. Perchance a youth raises a dissenting voice based on the past history, that youth might be accused of being antinational and charged with sedition. Nowadays, certain words like democracy, freedom, justice, or unity have been bent, shaped, and manipulated to serve as tools for domination, as meaningless tags that can be used to justify any action.

b. Polarization

The second trend that hinders social friendship is the employment of hyperbole, extremism, and polarization. A strategy of suspicion and criticism in a variety of ways is

utilized by one community to deny the right to exist of another community. Victory consists in eliminating one's opponents. In such ambience, to recognize one's neighbors or to assist those who have fallen along the way seems impossible. To care for the world in which human beings live means to care for the human beings. Such care does not constitute the agenda of economic powers. Often the objections registered in defense of the environment are silenced. Persons are no longer counted as a paramount value to be interested in, cared for, and respected. The poor, disabled, not yet useful the unborn, and no more useful the old are dispensed. "A decline in the birthrate, which leads to the aging of the population, together with the relegation of the elderly to a sad and lonely existence, is a subtle way of stating that it is all about us, that our individual concerns are the only thing that matters" (FT 19). A readiness to discard others finds expression in racism. Every human being receives rights on account of being born as a human being. However, in practice, human rights are not equal for all human beings. The organization of societies worldwide does not reflect clearly that women possess the same dignity and identical rights as men. Today children, women, and men of all ages are deprived of freedom and forced to live in conditions akin to slavery. Wars, terrorist attacks, racial or religious persecutions destroy human dignity. There exist ancestral fears like that of ghost. Outside the ancient town walls lies the territory of the unknown. Whatever comes from there cannot be trusted. Fear psychosis exercises complete control. "As a result, new walls are erected for self-preservation, the outside world ceases to exist and leaves only "my" world, to the point that others, no longer considered human beings possessed of an inalienable dignity, become only "them"" (FT 27).

c. Moral Deterioration

The third trend that distracts fraternity forms moral deterioration. The moral deterioration influences international action and a weakening of spiritual values as well as responsibility. In today's world, the sense of belonging to a single human family is fading.

There reigns a cool, comfortable, and globalized indifference. The gap between concern for one's personal well-being and the prosperity of the larger human family seems to be stretching to the point of complete division between individual and human community. Technology is constantly advancing, yet "how wonderful it would be if the growth or scientific and technological innovation could come with more equality and social inclusion. How wonderful would it be, even as we discover faraway planets, to rediscover the needs of the brothers and sisters who orbit around us" (FT 31).

d. Calamities

The fourth trend that disturbs social friendship constitutes calamities in history. For example, the world was relentlessly moving toward an economy that sought to reduce human costs. There were those who believed that freedom of the market was sufficient to keep everything secure. Yet, the unforeseen blow of the present uncontrolled pandemic Covid-19 forced to recover the concern for human beings, for everyone, rather than for the benefit of a few. "Aside from the different ways that various countries responded to the crisis, their inability to work together became quite evident. For all our hyper-connectivity, we witnessed a fragmentation that made it difficult to resolve problems that affect us all" (FT 7).

e. Absence of Human Dignity

The fifth trend that disrupts fraternity is the absence of human dignity on the borders. Many migrants have fled on account of wars, persecutions, and natural catastrophes. Others migrate speculating opportunities for themselves and their families to be well off. Some are attracted by Western culture, sometimes with unrealistic expectations, that expose them to grave disappointments. Those who emigrate experience separation from their place of origin and a cultural

as well as religious uprooting. Fragmentation is felt by their communities and by their children they leave behind. In some host countries, migration causes fear and alarm. “Migrants are not seen as entitled like others to participate in the life of society, and it is forgotten that they possess the same intrinsic dignity as any person” (FT 39). Some people are hesitant and fearful with regard to migrants.

f. Digital Media

The sixth trend that interrupts social friendship forms digital media. Digital media can expose human beings to the risk of addiction, isolation, and a gradual loss of contact with concrete reality. Digital media lack physical gestures, facial expressions, moments of silence, body language, smells, trembling of hands, blushes, perspiration, all these are parts of human communication. Digital relationships have the appearance of sociability, yet they do not really build community. “Digital connectivity is not enough to build bridges. It is not capable of uniting humanity” (FT 43). Individuals can choose a form of constant bonding through digital media that encourages hostility, insult, abuse, defamation, and verbal violence, destructive of others. “Social aggression has found unparalleled room for expansion through computers and mobile devices” (FT 44). These closed circuits facilitate the spread of fake news and false information, fomenting prejudice and hate. Unpleasant or disagreeable persons or situations are deleted in today’s virtual networks; a virtual circle is then created, isolating the human beings from the real world in which they are living. We must realize that “The flood of information at our finger tips does not make for greater wisdom. Wisdom is not born of quick searches on the internet nor is it a mass of unverified data. That is not the way to mature in the encounter with truth” (FT 50).

g. Self-Contempt

The seventh trend that blocks fraternity constitutes self-contempt. Certain economically prosperous countries are proposed as cultural models to developing countries. A desire to imitate

others on the part of the developing countries leads to copying rather than creating. This aping attitude fosters low national self-esteem. In the affluent sectors of many poor countries, there is a resistance to native ways of thinking and acting; there is a tendency to look down on one's own cultural identity. Destroying self-esteem forms an easy way to dominate others. There exists no worst form of alienation than to feel uprooted, belonging to no one.

2. The Paths of Hope: The Parable of the Good Samaritan

Despite these seven dark clouds elaborated by the Pope, which I have summarized in the First Part, he would like to discuss new paths of hope, because he believes that God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness in human family. In his attempt to search for a ray of light, he has recourse to the parable, told by Jesus and preserved by Evangelist Luke in 10:25-37, diffused with the title 'The Good Samaritan.' This parable responds to the query made by a lawyer, "Who is my neighbor?" (Luke 10:29)? This parable constitutes the biblical underpinning of *Fratelli Tutti*.

a. Neighbour

In the Israelite society, during the time of Jesus, the locution 'neighbor' usually meant individuals that lived in physical proximity of an Israelite. However, if these individuals did not belong to the race of that Israelite, then they were not identified as the Israelite's neighbors. For instance, the Samaritans were not considered members of the Israelites' own group.¹ A neighbor needs to be helped, but not the

¹ In 722 B.C., Assyria (Iraq of today) attacked the Northern Kingdom of Israel, whose capital city was Samaria and where 10 Tribes of Israel lived. Assyrian King Sargon II defeated Samaria. He took all the Israelite males away to Assyria and created male vacuum in Israel. He replenished the male vacuum by placing Assyrian males in Israel.

Samaritans. Thus, two criteria qualify someone as a neighbor: one, that person must be living in physically close vicinity and, two, that person must belong to the same ethnic clan. Based on so narrow definition, the Israelite may have just a handful of neighbors. The justification for not including the Samaritans in the category of neighbor consists in the fact that the Samaritans lived in a region, where non-Israelite rites were practiced. The Israelites gauged the Samaritans as impure, detestable, and dangerous. The Book of Sirach that came into existence in approximately 180 B.C., which is very close to the time of Jesus, mentions Samaria as “not even a people” (Sirach 50:25) and refers to the Samaritans as “the foolish people that live in Shechem” (Sirach 50:26). Such a condescending abhorrence prevailed among the Israelites for the Samaritans. Therefore, when Jesus requested for a drink from a Samaritan woman, she retorted curtly, “How is it that you, a Jew, ask a drink of me, a woman of Samaria” (John 4:9)? The epithet ‘Samaritan’ was employed by the Israelites to discredit Jesus, when they raised the

Being always dependent on males, Israelite females were compelled to enter into marital relationship with the Assyrian males. The generation that was born out of this wedlock had Assyrian fathers and Israelite mothers. The Encyclopedia recognizes this generation as the Lost Ten Tribes of Israel. In the eyes of the Southern Kingdom of Judah, whose capital city was Jerusalem and where 2 Tribes of Israel lived, this generation was mixed breed and, hence, impure. The Southern Kingdom gave them an insulting name ‘Samaritans’ based on the name of their capital city Samaria. The 2 Tribes of the Southern Kingdom count themselves pure breed. Therefore, they do not eat with the Samaritans or have marriage contracts with them or even touch them. The Samaritans lived primarily in Samaria Province in the time of Jesus. They considered themselves as true Israel and the Israelites as splinter group. The Samaritan Temple was on Mount Gerizim. The Samaritans recognized the Jerusalem Temple of the Israelites as a secondary sanctuary built by heretics. The Samaritans accepted only the Pentateuch as the Scripture, which differed in key points from that of the Israelites. Violent confrontations took place between the Israelites and the Samaritans throughout the 1st century A.D. (See Luke 9:52, 53; John 4:9; 8:48).

rhetorical question, “Are we not right in saying that you are a Samaritan and have a demon” (John 8:48)?

b. No Indifference

God neither upholds nor approves discrimination among human beings. God opposes the indifference between two persons. The Bible makes amply clear this personality trait of God in the primeval history (Genesis 1-11). In the anthropogenic myth that elucidates the sibling rivalry and ensuing fratricide, God takes the center stage when God addresses the poignant question to Cain, “Where is your brother Abel” (Genesis 4:9)? By this interrogation, God leaves no room for an appeal to determinism or fatalism as a justification for indifference. Instead, God encourages human beings to create a counter culture, in which they resolve their conflicts and care for one another. The rationale for such a counter culture consists in the one Creator of all human beings as asserted by Job in reference to his slaves, “Did not he who made me in the womb make them? And did not one fashion us in the womb” (Job 31:15)? Saint Irenaeus stressed the same thought by using the image of melody, “One who seeks the truth should not concentrate on the differences between one note and another, thinking as if each was created separately and apart from the others; instead, he should realise that one and the same person composed the entire melody” (Quoted in FT 58). The biblical underpinning of *Fratelli Tutti* comes from Wisdom Literature (i.e., Job) that all human beings are created by one and the same Creator. The human beings could be playing distinct roles in the society, but those roles do not provide platform for discriminations. All human beings are equal in dignity. No one is higher; no one is lower. No one is outsider; no one is insider. The Creator wants a human being should have concern for the other human being. Indifference toward the other human being is depreciated by the Creator in Genesis.

God asked in Genesis, “Where is your brother?” Instead of answering that question, the lawyer counter questions in the Gospel, “Who is my neighbor?” Pope Francis answers in his Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* and demonstrates the steps to become brothers and sisters to each other.²

c. Love Your Neighbor

When the Israelites experienced God tangibly in their liberation from slavery in Egypt, they entered into covenantal relationship with God to express their gratitude. One of the stipulations the Israelites acquiesced reads, “You shall love your neighbor as yourself” (Leviticus 19:18). The Book of Leviticus is one of the Five Books of the Pentateuch, which is Torah.³ Torah has the highest authority. The neighbor in this divine dictum was understood as referring to one’s fellow citizens. The Israelites living outside the land of Israel gradually expanded the boundaries of fellow citizens. One such Israelite living in the exile is Tobit from the tribe of Naphtali. He is mentioned as the protagonist of the book named after him. The book belongs to a section of the Bible called Historical Books. Tobit passes on the same command to his son Tobias as parental instruction in negative mood, “what you hate, do not do to anyone” (Tobit 4:15). This instruction is relevant to every human being. Commenting on this precept in 1st century B.C., Rabbi Hillel stated, “This is the entire Torah. Everything else is commentary” (Quoted in FT 59). Sirach, the sage of Israel, imparts the wisdom, “The compassion of human beings is for their neighbors, but the compassion of the Lord is for every living thing” (Sirach 18:13).

² In the Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, the Pope writes chapters on Envisaging and Engendering an Open World (paragraphs 87-127), A Heart Open to the Whole World (paragraphs 128-153), A Better Kind of Politics (paragraphs 154-197), Dialogue and Friendship in Society (paragraphs 198-224), Paths of Renewed Encounter (paragraphs 225-270), Religions at the Service of Fraternity in our World (paragraphs 271-287).

³ Torah or Pentateuch means Genesis, Exodus, Leviticus, Numbers, and Deuteronomy of the Old Testament.

As a result, the desire among the Israelites to imitate God's *modus operandi* gradually replaced their tendency to love only those who were geographically nearest to them. Along with the passing of time, the comprehension of the Israelites with regard to the interpersonal relationship among human beings steadily developed. The neighbor in the statute 'love your neighbor' involves every human being. The understanding of neighbor in the law of Leviticus is expanded in the Historical Book of Tobit and is made to include every human being in the Wisdom Literature (i.e. Sirach). The definition of neighbor kept on broadening slowly and steadily.

d. The Golden Rule

Rabbi Hillel's ordinance is articulated positively in the New Testament, "In everything do to others as you would have them do to you; for this is the law and the prophets" (Matthew 7:10). This norm is called Golden Rule and is based on the heavenly Father's comportment, who "makes his sun rise on the evil and on the good, and sends rain on the righteous and on the unrighteous" (Matthew 5:45). The heavenly Father does not discriminate any human being based on any issue. He lets flow His mercy on every human being, irrespective of human being's righteousness or unrighteousness. Human beings are summoned to emulate the heavenly Father, "Be merciful, just as your Father is merciful" (Luke 6:36). As is the Father, so, are His children. The New Testament counts every human being as the child of our Father; therefore, every human being becomes our sister or brother.

e. Rationale for Fraternity

The Old Testament provides a reason for becoming magnanimous to embrace foreigners in the historical datum, viz., the Israelites themselves had once lived as foreigners in

Egypt. Exodus 20:22-23:33 is identified as Covenant Code.⁴ The Covenant Code constitutes an exposition and application of the Decalogue (Exodus 20:2-17). The Covenant Code contains apodictic laws. An apodictic law is a genre, which deals with the general and not particular. The apodictic laws are categorical in texture and unconditional in formulation, making absolute demand. Two such apodictic laws that are humanitarian in nature attach the rationale for the demand made, “You shall not wrong or oppress a resident alien, for you were aliens in the land of Egypt” (Exodus 22:21) and “You shall not oppress a resident alien; you know the heart of an alien, for you were aliens in the land of Egypt” (Exodus 23:9).

Leviticus 17-26 is named Holiness Code. The Holiness Code includes casuistic laws. A casuistic law is a genre, which deals with the particular and not general. The casuistic laws are hypothetical in texture and conditional in formulation. The casuistic laws present specific cases that require legal decision and prescribe appropriate verdict as well as penalty. For example, “When an alien resides with you in your land, you shall not oppress the alien. The alien who resides with you shall be to you as the citizen among you; you shall love the alien as yourself, for you were aliens in the land of Egypt” (Leviticus 19:33-34). In this summons, reference to the exodus experience induces the Israelites to copy the divine action in freeing them.

Deuteronomy 12-26 is termed Deuteronomic Code. The Deuteronomic Code has more humanitarian concern than that of the Covenant Code (Exodus 20:22-23:33). In the Deuteronomic Code, the relationship with the marginalized is guided by Israel’s own experience of God acting on its behalf in Egypt. This appeal to Israel’s own experience in Egypt is emphasized by repetition and extension. The persons, who must be paid special attention,

⁴ The Pentateuch contains 5 Codes of Laws as follows: Decalogue (Exodus 20:2-17), Covenant Code (Exodus 20:22-23:33), Ritual Decalogue (Exodus 34:10-26), Holiness Code (Leviticus 17-26), Deuteronomic Code (Deuteronomy 12-26).

subsume the least powerful members of the society such as slaves, widows, orphans, needy, poor, and strangers. Observance of the law is, thus, both a response to and an imitation of what God had done for the Israelites in emancipating them from Egypt, e.g., “When you gather the grapes of your vineyard, do not glean what is left, it shall be for the alien, the orphan, and the widow. Remember that you were a slave in the land of Egypt; therefore I am commanding you to do this” (Deuteronomy 24:21-22). Thus, Covenant Code, Holiness Code, Deuteronomic Code of the Pentateuch demonstrate God’s action on behalf of the Israelites, when the latter were slaves in the land of Egypt, as the model for the Israelites to follow vis-à-vis the non-Israelites.

f. Love Builds Bridges

Paul, a Pharisee, who obeyed all 613 commandments of the Old Testament⁵ in minutest detail, had an encounter with the Risen Lord (see Acts 9:1-19). As a consequence, Paul was converted in his belief that no amount of works can earn salvation. He began teaching that all Christians are free from the law. If the law had been able to save, there was no need for Paul to become believer in Jesus. If the law had been able to save, Jesus Himself had died in vain. Salvation ensues not by observing the Mosaic Law, but by an act of faith in Jesus. Far from being called to a freedom that leads to license, Christians are summoned to a proper use of their freedom, which is a freedom, through the Spirit, for love. Freedom from law is freedom for love. The contrast between freedom that leads to license and freedom that leads to love is brought out in the contrast between the flesh and the spirit. Paul explicates that freedom from the law does not mean freedom for a life of self indulgence. Those who die with Christ die

⁵ Later Israelite tradition enumerates 613 commandments given by God through Moses in the Pentateuch. Out of 613 commandments, 250 prescribe “Do” and 363 prohibit “Do not.”

to the flesh and live with the power of Jesus given through the Spirit. The Christians must walk by the Spirit. Paul insists that there is no eternal life without the works of the Spirit. Paul does not contradict himself. When he declares that no works can earn salvation, he means that strict adherence to the law per se may not be possible, given the fragile nature of human beings. If somebody succeeds in prevailing over her/his concupiscence, then salvation would become her/his remuneration. The non-Israelites, who are deprived of the Mosaic Law, may remain out of the scope of salvation. Our God is not partisan God. Salvation is meant for every human being. Paul exhorts to do the works of the Spirit. These works allow the human beings to experience salvation that is given as a gift from God. Let me offer an analogy: Suppose I am invited to dine with the Pope, which is a gift, I would clean myself up, dress up according to the occasion, learn the table manners, pick up the etiquette, by heart some vocabulary of the Pope's mother tongue. All these works I do because I have a banquet with the Pope; it is not on account of these works that I will be rewarded with that dinner. These are called the works of the Spirit. Those who receive the gift of faith in Jesus, who is the manifestation of the Father's love, are expected to manifest in their lives that love. So, Paul exhorts, "the whole law is summed up in a single commandment, "You shall love your neighbor as yourself" (Galatians 5:14). In eternal life, only love endures (see 1 Corinthians 13:13). If that love I practice here in this earthly life, I anticipate the eternal life here on earth.

In Johannine community, the call to fraternal love is echoed, employing the metaphors of light and darkness, life and death. For example, "Whoever loves a brother or sister lives in the light, and in such a person there is no cause for stumbling. But whoever hates another believer is in the darkness" (1 John 2:10-11). "We know that we have passed from death to life because we love one another. Whoever does not love abides in death" (1 John 3:14). The author, then, draws the climactic conclusion, declaring, "those who do not love a brother or sister whom they have seen,

cannot love God whom they have not seen” (1 John 4:20). According to this teaching, my love for the human being whom I see manifests my love for God whom I do not see. Such a pragmatic lesson is substantiated by a Gujarati saying *Janseva Aej Prabhuseva* “Serving people is equal to serving God.”

This imperative to love could be misunderstood. Recognizing the temptation of the earliest Christian communities to form clicks and isolated circles, Paul, a man of prayer, beseeches, “may the Lord make you increase and abound in love for one another and for all” (1 Thessalonians 3:12). Instruction to love must not engender ghetto mentality. Love does not envisage barriers; instead, love envisages bridges. In the Johannine community everyone is exhorted with this dictum, “Beloved, you do faithfully whatever you do for the friends, even though they are strangers to you” (3 John 5). Pauline and Johannine texts note that love does not care if a brother or sister in need comes from one place or another. This is precisely what the four Spanish Nuns did in 1950 when they embarked from Spain and landed in Gujarat to work for the lepers. “Love shatters the chains that keep us isolated and separate; in their place, it builds bridges. Love enables us to create one great family, where all of us can feel at home” (Quoted in FT 62).

3. The Perusal of the Parable

With the above-elucidated biblical understanding of the neighbor and love, let us peruse the parable of the Good Samaritan. In the parable, a priest and a Levite holding significant social positions passed by the injured lying on the wayside. They did not spend a couple of minutes, caring for the injured or even in calling for the help. Only the Samaritan stopped at the sight of the injured, approached him, cared for him, paid for his need, and gave him his (the Samaritan’s) time. The Samaritan might have had his plans for that day,

his own commitments for that hour. He was able to put all that aside, when he was confronted with someone in need.

Let us examine ourselves: Out of these three characters, viz., the priest, the Levite, and the Samaritan, to whom do we resemble? Like the priest and the Levite in the parable, we are constantly tempted to ignore others, especially the weak. Though we have made progress, we are still illiterate, when we have to accompany, care for, and support the frailest and vulnerable members of our societies. We have become accustomed to look the other way, to pass by, to avoid. Looking the other way, passing by, avoiding illustrate our approach to life that throbs in the other. Such approach to life spells the symptom of an unhealthy community. The parable persuades us to rediscover our vocation as citizens of our nation, as builders of a new social bond. This summons is grounded in a fundamental law of our being: we are called to direct society to the pursuit of the common good. By his actions, the Samaritan demonstrated that “life is not simply time that passes; life is a time for interactions” (FT 66). The parable presents the basic decision we need to make in order to rebuild our wounded world. That decision is to imitate the Samaritan. “The parable shows us how a community can be rebuilt by men and women who identify with the vulnerability of others, who reject the creation of a society of exclusion, and act instead as neighbours, lifting up and rehabilitating the fallen for the sake of the common good” (FT 67).

The characters in the parable transmute, once they face the pathetic sight of the injured on the roadside. The distinction between Israelite and Samaritan, priest and laity fades into insignificance. Now, there are only two kinds of characters: one kind stops, another kind passes by; one kind bends down to help, another kind looks the other way to hurry off. Anyone, who is neither a robber nor a passerby in the parable, is either an injured or taking care of an injured. In this parable, Jesus does not offer alternatives; He encourages us to persevere in love to restore dignity to the suffering. From human perspective whatever we

may be, based on our caste, creed, culture, color, country, Jesus wants us to be the character taking care of the last, the least, and the lost.

The robbers in the parable are the dark shadows of neglect and violence, descending on our world, in the service of petty interests of power, gain, and division. Seven such trends are depicted in the First Part that act as robbers for our world today. We may be functioning as robbers captured in those seven trends, hindering social friendship. The passersby in the parable are a priest and a Levite, who are religious and devoted to the worship of God. Their act of passing by evinces that belief in God and the worship of God are not enough parameters to ensure that one is actually living in a way pleasing to God. Saint John Chrysostom expressed the same thought creatively, “Do you wish to honour the body of the Saviour? Do not despise it when it is naked. Do not honour it in church with silk vestments while outside it is naked and numb with cold” (Quoted in FT 74). The passersby reflect the growing gulf between ourselves and the world around us. The passing by can be through retreating inwards, ignoring others, being indifferent to their plight, or looking elsewhere.

Today, we have a great opportunity to be Good Samaritans, who bear the pain of other people’s troubles. Like the Samaritan in the parable, we need only to have a pure and simple desire to be a community that is constant and tireless in the effort to include, integrate, and lift up the fallen. We can commence to perform at the most concrete and local level, maybe our own families, and, then, expand to the farthest reaches of our countries and our world with the same care and concern that the Samaritan exhibited for each of the wounds of the injured. At micro level, the injured represents a single victim; at macro level, the injured represents the country. The many wounds of the injured represent

innumerable men and women that need our nursing and nourishing, care and concern, energy and encouragement, supply and support. It is true what we sing: ‘The world stands in need of liberation my Lord, it still has to feel Your power.’ The Samaritan in the parable discovered an innkeeper, who would care for the injured; so, we, too, are called to act not as individuals but as a community. Let us seek out others of good will that God has planted in human hearts. The Samaritan departed without expecting any recognition or gratitude. All of us have a responsibility for the wounded world. The principle of *Nishkam Karma*, i.e., doing the duty without expecting any reward, proposed by the Sacred Scripture of Hindu Religion *Sheemad Bhagvad Gita*, was adopted by the Samaritan. Let us emulate this Samaritan in our lives. While teaching His disciples, Jesus imparted the lesson not to expect ‘thanks’ and quoted a slave’s routine experience of not receiving ‘thanks’ from her/his master for the work done: “So you also, when you have done all that you were ordered to do, say, ‘We are worthless slaves; we have done only what we ought to have done” (Luke 17:10)! Jesus counsels us not to wait for the gesture of gratitude from beneficiaries of our charity, for to do charity is our duty. The one in need deserves my aid; I should not aspire for her/his acknowledgement or recognition.

Jesus concludes the parable, instructing, “Go and do likewise” (Luke 10:37). Jesus challenges us to put aside all differences, divisions, denominations and, in the face of suffering, to draw near to others with no question asked. “I should no longer say that I have neighbours to help, but that I must myself be a neighbour to others” (FT 81). The definition of neighbor based on this parable could be: See not who your neighbor is; see whose neighbor you are. Jesus admonishes us to become neighbor to anyone, who requires our physical, psychological, emotional, spiritual, familial, social, financial support.

4. Jesus Identifies with the Suffering

In His Eschatological Discourse (Matthew 23-25), Jesus dramatizes the scene of the Last Judgment through a parable in Matthew 25:31-46. In that parable Jesus says, “I was a stranger and you welcomed me” (Matthew 25:35). Jesus, being sensitive to the plights and predicaments of others, can identify Himself with a stranger. When the persecutor Saul interrogated the identity of the complaining voice, “Who are you, Lord?” (Acts 9:5a), the Risen Lord responded, “I am Jesus, whom you are persecuting” (Acts 9:5b). Jesus identifies with the persecuted Church. The victim is Jesus and vice versa. Paul exhorts, “Rejoice with those who rejoice, weep with those who weep” (Romans 12:15). In this section, Romans 12:3-13:14, Paul articulates the basic demands of Christian living. Paul indicates genuine love as the quality distinctive of believers. Love represents the outflow in believers’ own lives of the divine love, going beyond mere words to embrace the enemy. Love does not passively wait for an occasion to arise; love actively seeks for an opportunity to operate. Such eagerness constitutes an effect and a sign of the Spirit’s working. One finds harder to rejoice in another’s joy than to feel sorry for her/his misfortune. To feel what the other feels is called sympathy (same pathos). The sympathy requires that one goes beyond oneself and one’s own immediate concern. The sympathy forms the basis of true agape in action. Love is not mere emotion, but an action. Everyone is not to think exactly alike, but legitimate diversity of view is to be encompassed with an aspiration of unity. A Gujarati aphorism paraphrases the same thought, which I translate into English: There can be differences of opinions; there should not be divisions of hearts.

Christ identifies Himself with the injured and the Christian living demands to serve the injured; therefore, the Christians

have to become the Good Samaritan of the parable. The words of Jesus, “Truly I tell you, just as you did it to one of the least of these who are members of my family, you did it to me” (Matthew 25:40), compel the Christians to recognize Christ in each of the abandoned sisters and brothers. Believers in God, the theists, know that God loves every human being with infinite love. We, the Christians, believe that Christ shed his blood on the cross for each of us and that no one is excluded from the sphere of His universal love. The ultimate source of that love is the very life of the triune God. We, the Christians, encounter in the community of the three divine Persons the origin and perfect model of life in society. “For this reason, it is important that catechesis and preaching speak more directly and clearly about the social meaning of existence, the fraternal dimension of spirituality, our conviction of the inalienable dignity of each person, and our reasons for loving and accepting all our brothers and sisters” (FT 86). God is the Creator of all human beings. Any human being who believes in God as the Father accepts the responsibility of becoming sister/brother of all human beings in general and of the marginalized in particular.

Conclusion

The seven dark clouds of national interest, polarization, moral deterioration, calamities, absence of human dignity, digital media, self-contempt act as robbers of the parable of the Good Samaritan. They obstruct universal fraternity and social friendship. In the vein of the priest and the Levite of the parable, we have the proclivity to pass by. Jesus challenges us to be the Good Samaritan of the parable. To challenge us, Jesus amplifies the definition of neighbor and admonishes us to see whose neighbor we are rather than to see who our neighbor is. Love constitutes our response to God, who expressed God’s love for us by sending God’s only Son Jesus to us. Jesus manifests God’s love for us in concrete actions. Love can be responded only with love. We are called to articulate our love for God in our love for human beings, especially the downtrodden. We are invited to

associate with human beings of good will, sown in them by the same God, and work as a family to reach out the wounded world. We have the responsibility toward each other as we are all created by God our Father, bonding us all as sisters and brothers. In this family, the cry of the hour is: Do become the Good Samaritan; do not become the passerby.

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